

WHITE PAPER

OPEN DATA IN THE ENERGY STORAGE COMMUNITY

StoRIES

Storage Research Infrastructure Eco-System

October 2025

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White paper: "Open data in the energy storage community",

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Executive Summary

This white paper brings together experts from the energy storage research community to promote better use and sharing of data. It focuses on improving FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) and best practices for storage research data to promote and assure data openness. The document examines the current state of open and FAIR data in energy storage research, highlights existing gaps, and explores future opportunities. It concludes with key challenges and practical recommendations to contribute to the advancement of FAIR practices and open data in the field of energy storage.

Keywords: FAIR, open data, storage, energy metadata; data standards; energy storage research

1. Introduction and objectives

Energy storage plays a pivotal role in enabling the widespread adoption of renewable energy, supporting electric mobility, and ensuring the stability and resilience of modern power grids. Research and development in this field generate vast and heterogeneous datasets, spanning the entire innovation chain, from materials discovery and synthesis, through physicochemical and electrochemical characterization, to device design, performance evaluation, degradation analysis, and lifecycle or techno-economic assessments. However, these datasets are often produced using diverse experimental setups, instruments, and data formats, and are documented with inconsistent metadata standards. This lack of uniformity hinders data interoperability, reproducibility, and long-term accessibility, ultimately slowing scientific progress and innovation.

To overcome these challenges and assure effective data openness, the implementation of FAIR data principles, ensuring that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, is becoming increasingly essential. Applying these principles promotes standardized data management, facilitates automated data mining and machine learning approaches, and enables efficient knowledge sharing across disciplines. Establishing robust data infrastructures, ontologies, and community-driven standards for energy storage research will be critical to accelerating discovery and improving the design and sustainability of next-generation energy storage technologies.

Complementing open data, the **FAIR data principles** add critical layers of structure and re-usability of data. FAIR emphasizes contextualization through metadata, adherence to community standards, and compatibility with computational tools. While FAIR does not require the open availability of data [Mons et al.,2017], it instead emphasises findability, accessibility, and reuse, even if the data (and its metadata) is not open or free. In general, FAIR data requires to have a clear, preferably machine readable, license. The shift from open to FAIR thus requires a cultural transformation—one that values data stewardship as an integral part of the research process.

The energy storage community is shifting to value data sharing for collaboration and innovation, supported by initiatives like StoRIES. Implementing FAIR principles, while challenging, can improve product development for battery and fuel cell companies and data discovery. Despite concerns over IP (Intellectual Property) and commercial sensitivity, the FAIR framework allows for proprietary data to be described for discovery. Moreover, digitalization trends further necessitate the integration of machine-actionable data through FAIR practices.

This White Paper also benefits from the outcome of other initiatives (European Materials Modelling Ontology – EMMO; European Open Science Cloud - EOSC; Characterization Data - CHADA; Novel Materials Discovery - NOMAD; EERADATA; Nexus; IUPAC; CODATA; GAIA-X) aimed at overcoming these challenges through the development of a comprehensive metadata framework and an AI-driven data management platform tailored to the energy and materials communities at large.

The **metadata framework and ontologies**, co-designed with domain experts, offer a modular and extensible schema for capturing experimental and computational data in battery research. It aligns with existing ontologies and standards, while remaining flexible enough to accommodate diverse research workflows. By providing templates, controlled vocabularies, and guidance for metadata entry, the framework enables researchers to describe their data in a way that supports FAIR compliance and interoperability.

Building on this framework, the project developed a **user-centric data management platform** for the StoRIES community based on the VIMILABS¹ technologies and services. The new platform provides easy-to-use AI tools that help researchers upload, organize, and describe their data more efficiently. It supports smart categorization, assists with adding metadata, and includes advanced search features, such as semantic search, which lets users find relevant data using both keywords and structured queries. By making FAIR data management simpler, the platform lowers the barrier for researchers to participate in good data stewardship. It also offers a shared infrastructure that supports collaboration, data-driven discoveries, and digital innovation across the energy storage community.

This white paper outlines the current landscape of FAIR and open data in energy storage, highlights best practices and case studies, and identifies ongoing challenges and limitations. It presents new contributions in the form of a metadata framework and an AI-powered data management platform that enhance research collaboration. By adopting FAIR data practices and participating in the shared data ecosystem, researchers and industry stakeholders can accelerate innovation, improve reproducibility, and help build a sustainable energy future. Next steps involve expanding tools, training, and international cooperation on FAIR data infrastructure.

¹ <https://vimi.ai/>

2. The landscape of FAIR data management in energy systems/storage

Energy storage management systems often rely on proprietary, fragmented datasets lacking granularity and FAIRification, limiting utility and accessibility, exacerbated by privacy concerns and a culture resistant to data sharing.

Open access data is characterized by fragmented repositories in the energy storage sector, with no unified strategy for their development and for their reuse (Maretti et al., 2021). There are several open data repositories in a central (e.g. Zenodo), and local level, e.g. hosted by universities and public bodies. However, open data use also shows significant obstacles due to a lack of awareness, technical expertise, and established metadata practices to facilitate re-use. The research community often struggles with aligning their practices with FAIR principles (Wilkinson, 2016) due to a lack of coordination, common standardized methodologies, and a lack of sharing experience with methods of metadata application.

Preparing datasets for sharing based on FAIR principles needs time and resources. Sometimes, the availability and usability of such data vary significantly across the energy storage community due to the lack of standardization and common metadata and ontology, and limited adherence to FAIR principles yet. Lack of standardization makes difficult interoperability necessary to integrate or reuse datasets coming from diverse sources. Thus, an incomplete system of metadata and ontology is another obstacle for the quality, integration, validation, and reusing data. For this reason, it is necessary to develop a unified metadata and ontology for energy storage related data (Michiorri et al., 2022). Moreover, the accessibility is a major challenge in achieving FAIR compliance in the energy storage community, hindered by limited funding, expertise, and fragmented data.

Developing robust FAIR data practices and partnerships with data producers is strategic, along with creating a repository to improve access and sharing. Several leading case studies illustrate the potential of open-source and FAIR-aligned data management in the energy storage sector. For example:

- The Materials Project has made vast amounts of computational materials data freely available, supporting the design of new battery materials.
- Battery Archive provides open access to experimental cycling data, with standardized metadata and visualization tools.
- Big Map is a large-scale European initiative focused on developing interoperable data infrastructures and ontologies for battery materials discovery.
- Danish Battery Database and NREL's Battery Data Repository show case government-led efforts to curate open datasets that serve both academic and industrial users.

These platforms demonstrate the benefits of structured, accessible data in accelerating innovation, improving reproducibility, and fostering collaboration. They also highlight the need for sustained

investment, user-friendly tools, and governance models that ensure data quality and long-term availability.

A growing number of open-source tools and datasets are available to support FAIR data management in energy storage. These include among the others:

- AiiDA is a workflow engine for reproducible computational science, used in materials simulations.
- Pymatgen and Matminer are Python libraries for materials data mining and analysis.
- Battery Archive and BEEP are tools for standardizing and analysing battery cycling data.
- OpenBATT is a platform for data sharing and collaboration in battery testing.

These tools provide essential infrastructure for data handling, but they also vary widely in terms of user interface, metadata support, and interoperability. As such, ongoing efforts are needed to evaluate, harmonize, and extend these resources in line with FAIR principles.

3. FAIR data in StoRIES, identify gaps and strenghts

Key challenges in implementing FAIR and open data management within the energy storage community participating in the StoRIES project were systematically identified and analyzed through a comprehensive gap analysis. This activity aimed to assess the status of data practices across the consortium, highlighting barriers to data sharing, standardization, and reuse. To ensure a representative overview, an extensive survey on FAIR and Open (FAIR/O) data management was conducted, engaging nearly all StoRIES partners, both core and associated. The survey collected information on existing data workflows, metadata practices, infrastructure availability, and levels of awareness and implementation of FAIR principles. The outcomes of this analysis provide valuable insights into common bottlenecks, such as the lack of harmonized metadata standards, limited interoperability between repositories, and varying levels of data literacy, thereby guiding the development of targeted actions to improve data governance and foster a more open and collaborative research environment within the energy storage community.

Moreover, the study identified that certain aspects make a particularly strong contribution to the effective implementation of the FAIR data principles within the energy storage research community. Specifically:

- **Findability:** aspects related to the quality, completeness, and standardization of metadata, which ensure that datasets can be easily discovered, indexed, and cited by both humans and machines.
- **Interoperability:** aspects associated with the use of controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and standardized tagging schemas that define data elements and metadata, thereby enabling meaningful connections and integration with other datasets and information sources.
- **Accessibility:** aspects concerning the degree to which data can be retrieved and accessed through well-documented and sustainable mechanisms, without the need for proprietary software or specialized tools once access authorization has been granted.

Conversely, other factors were found to make a lower relative contribution to the practical implementation of FAIR principles in the energy storage domain. These include:

- The assignment of **persistent identifiers** to datasets.
- The **format** in which datasets are stored or exchanged.
- The **methods and tools** used to capture and structure information for future reuse.
- The type of **repository** or registry where metadata are recorded.
- The availability of **metadata** even when the associated data are no longer accessible.
- The use of standardized **licensing** frameworks, such as Creative Commons licenses, to specify conditions for data reuse.

While these latter elements remain essential components of a fully FAIR-compliant data management framework, the analysis indicates that improvements in metadata quality, semantic interoperability, and accessibility protocols currently offer the highest potential impact for advancing FAIR and Open Data implementation within the energy storage community.

The results of the gap analysis revealed the following key conclusions:

- **Strengths.** The main strengths identified within the community relate to the presence of structured, open-standard, and well-formatted datasets, as well as the use of established vocabularies, ontologies, and tagging schemas to define data elements and metadata. These practices contribute significantly to improving data consistency, discoverability, and potential interoperability across research activities.
- **Opportunities.** The primary opportunities lie in the broader adoption of FAIR principles within the energy storage community and the increased availability of FAIR and open data across the wider energy research ecosystem. This enhanced openness would enable greater data reuse, foster collaborative development, and promote the interoperability and exchange of datasets linked through standardized metadata and ontological frameworks. Ultimately, these improvements are expected to lead to reduced redundancy, enhanced research efficiency, and greater transparency throughout the data lifecycle.

4. FAIR data gaps: the state of the art in the community

During the StoRIES project, awareness of importance of applying FAIR principles is growing in the energy storage community, still, implementation often lags due to a lack of knowledge, tools, incentives, accessibility, low standardization of metadata collection and access, and uncoordinated efforts.

Frequently, the difficulty for accessibility datasets is due to constrained by proprietary restrictions, institutional policies, the fragmentation of data across different platforms, and the scarcity of publicly, open, and available datasets.

One of the key enablers of FAIR data is the use of rich, structured metadata that provides the necessary context for data interpretation and reuse. In response to this need, harmonized and standardized (Wierling et al., 2021) metadata schemas and domain-specific ontologies are being developed to support consistent data annotation. Ontologies such as OntoBattery and the Battery Interface Ontology (BattINFO) provide controlled vocabularies for describing materials, processes, and test conditions. These semantic tools are essential for enabling interoperability across datasets and systems. Efforts to harmonize metadata and ontologies across laboratories and institutions are gaining traction. Collaborative projects, standards development organizations, and research infrastructures are playing a key role in fostering convergence. However, widespread adoption requires community engagement, training, and the integration of semantic tools into everyday research workflows. Beyond the laboratories, there is also a need for semantic alignment in grid integration of hybrid storage solutions, affecting the interoperability of energy management systems and grid management. The Horizon Europe projects PARMENIDES, INTERSTORE, and int:n² support the enabling of interoperability.

Further, lack of standardization is a critical element of FAIR data implementation. In the energy storage domain, various standards have emerged for describing test procedures, material properties, and data formats. For example, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) has issued standards for battery testing, while initiatives like BattINFO and the Big Map project have proposed metadata and data exchange formats tailored to battery research. The lack of standardization limits the integration process among different datasets from diverse sources.

These efforts are helping to build a common language for the field, enabling better data comparability and integration. Yet, challenges remain in aligning national and international standards, bridging academic and industrial practices, and ensuring that standards are flexible enough to accommodate innovation. Community-driven initiatives that combine standards development with FAIR principles are particularly promising. By embedding standardization into

² https://community.intnet.eu/About/Vision_purpose

metadata frameworks and data management platforms, these efforts can provide practical tools that lower the barrier to adoption for researchers and engineers alike.

Aside from the importance of the standardization of the metadata collection protocols, a detailed screening was conducted to evaluate the current landscape of FAIR infrastructures and metadata schemes for materials characterization. The approach combined three methods: (1) literature review of frameworks from 2015–2024 (e.g., CHADA, NOMAD, Nexus, Materials Data Facility), (2) hands-on platform audits (EOSC, FAIRsharing, EERAdata), and (3) stakeholder input from eight consortium groups through interviews and workshops. Evaluation criteria included metadata completeness, machine-readability, semantic standardization, interoperability, and scalability.

The output of the screening concluded in a technical assessment focused on four aspects. First, it highlighted the importance of data size and formats powering the software ability to handle large datasets (hundreds of GB/days) in TIFF, MRC, HDF5, with and without compression. Secondly, the scope coverage of different characterization methods such as TEM, SEM, FIB, AFM, synchrotron, and neutron imaging. Then, the clarity and disposition of legal aspects such as licensing models, GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance, data-use agreements. Finally, it was assessed how access to these platforms were granted, based on standard protocols like APIs (REST/GraphQL), authentication (OAuth2), and query performance.

Findings showed that existing solutions have strengths but also critical gaps. CHADA tables cover methods well but lack machine-readability and APIs, providing only a structured and standardized metadata schema. NOMAD and Nexus support a wide range of modeling data, but they leave out other scientific fields, such as those specific to imaging. Materials Data Facility offers strong API tools but weak process-based structures. EOSC and FAIRsharing catalog standards but lack ingestion and semantic search. EERAdata is energy-focused but provides only basic metadata guidance, which was confirmed by pilot ingestions.

In general, the gap analysis identified four key shortcomings that are not being addressed by existing methods:

- 1- No automated conversion of structured metadata into graph models.
- 2- No dynamic, LLM-aided ontology alignment, leading to fragmented terminology.
- 3- Lack of hybrid semantic search (string + embedding-based).
- 4- Absence of end-to-end FAIR pipelines integrating metadata entry, ontology-driven storage, and AI-ready retrieval.

These gaps are promoted by traditional project-specific data systems that current projects are based leading to data fragmentation; FAIR principles and ontologies are essential to unify datasets. Ontologies like EMMO provide formal knowledge representation across fabrication, characterization, and simulation, enhancing interoperability. Graph databases, particularly Neo4j, offer flexible and natural handling of heterogeneous workflows compared to rigid relational or NoSQL models.

Furthermore, ontology quality is pivotal to ensure accuracy, completeness, consistency, precision, and traceability of the stored datasets. For the energy storage community, these indicators are critical for metadata reliability and can be used to assess the quality and effectiveness of the employed method across different fields.

Nowadays, generative AI (LLMs) plays a growing role in data pipelines, enabling autonomous extraction, ontology creation, and semantic search across domains. Techniques like embeddings and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) can fine-tune domain-specific ontologies, improve metadata quality, and support AI/ML applications at scale. These technologies emerge as pillar alternatives to automate the data ingestion, extraction, and transformation workflows to achieve a flexible but standardized metadata environment.

5. FAIR Data, from gaps to action

The StoRIES project identified several key gaps related to FAIR data practices in the energy storage community. These include data fragmentation and limited accessibility, a lack of standardization, and the absence of metadata schemas that are both machine-readable and human understandable. To address these challenges and help the community move toward shared and consistent management of experimental data, the StoRIES project has outlined the following key recommendations:

- **Ensure access to major funding opportunities for FAIR data adoption.** Major funding organizations, such as the European Union Horizon Programme and the Dutch Research Council (NWO), now require researchers to apply FAIR principles and make their data openly available. These funders also provide FAIR checklists for multiple disciplines (Adams et al., 2023) to guide researchers in making their data compliant.
- **Apply FAIR principles systematically, especially in EU-funded projects.** Integrating FAIR practices helps ensure that data are not only accessible but also usable and reusable. This approach strengthens collaboration, reproducibility, and scientific progress within the energy community. It also enhances data interoperability, making datasets easier to combine and reuse across other sectors.
- **Develop and compare harmonized Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for FAIR data.** Establishing standardized KPIs will enable the measurement and evaluation of progress toward FAIR data implementation (Otalvora et al., 2016). In the energy storage field, such KPIs can assess the effectiveness and impact of FAIR and open data initiatives.
- **Promote FAIR and open data sharing along the entire energy storage value chain.** The value chain spans all stages—from resource extraction and manufacturing to transportation, operation, and recycling. FAIR and open data are strategic at every level, ensuring equitable access, transparency, and compliance with GDPR requirements for data protection.
- **Advance semantic alignment and interoperability beyond the laboratory.** StoRIES recognizes the importance of consistent data semantics in the grid integration of hybrid storage solutions, which affect energy management and grid operations. Horizon Europe projects such as PARMENIDES, INTERSTORE, and int:net contribute to addressing these interoperability gaps.

Within StoRIES, efforts focus on developing metadata schemas that describe both inputs and outputs of individual methods or infrastructures. These schemas are represented in knowledge graphs to enhance machine readability and improve metadata interoperability across different platforms and infrastructures.

5.1 EXAMPLE: KPI'S OF PHYSICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for **Research Infrastructures (RIs)** are designed to evaluate the efficiency, impact, and success of the infrastructure in achieving its goals. These KPIs (see Appendix I) can vary depending on the type of infrastructure (e.g., energy, health, materials science), but they generally fall into the following dimensions: 1. Scientific & Research Impact; 2. User Engagement & Access; 3. Operational Efficiency & Availability; 4. Innovation & Technological Advancement; 5. Sustainability & Environmental Impact; 6. Impact on Education & Training; 7. Societal & Economic Impact; 8. Financial Sustainability; 9. Global Collaboration & Recognition; 10. Governance & Strategic Alignment.

Not all KPI's apply to all Research Infrastructures. Especially ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortia) and ESFRI (European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures) Research Infrastructures have a specific set of KPI's applicable to them. Once an ESFRI Research Infrastructure is fully implemented and operational ESFRI it becomes an ESFRI Landmark. From that point, in-person access' is increasingly also required to provide Open and FAIR data as part of their operation.

Physical Research Infrastructures can provide access to observational data as well as experimental data. The measurement of the FAIRness of the data provision is also becoming increasingly important.

The FAIRsFAIR “Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe” project funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 developed 17 core FAIR object assessment metrics within FAIRsFAIR, each corresponding to a part or the whole of one of the FAIR principles.

The FAIR principles apply to any digital objects. For physical Research Infrastructures are in the first place concerned with a subset of digital objects: research data that are collected, measured, or created for purposes of scientific analysis. However, once a physical Research Infrastructure starts to provide hybrid and/or digital services like simulations, digital twins, digital models, AI services for data analysis, verification, and generation, those also could become digital objects which are measured against the FAIR principles. The 17 core FAIR object assessment metrics identified by the FAIRsFAIR project are (Source FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics³. Please see Appendix I for a detail description of each indicator. Alternatively, you can use an automated tool like **Fuji**⁴. F-UJI is a web service to programmatically assess FAIRness of research data objects at the dataset level based on the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics.”

Another alternative is to use a combination of the Fuji FAIRness score together with individual KPI's based on a limited selection of the 17 core FAIR object assessment metrics (Appendix I).

³ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>

⁴ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

5.2 EXAMPLE: KPI'S OF ECCSEL

ECCSEL currently uses Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure physical access to its research infrastructure and has begun developing KPIs for virtual access, including those related to FAIRness (see Appendix I). With ECCSEL's designation as an ESFRI Landmark, an expanded and updated set of KPIs has been introduced.

Specific KPIs for assessing FAIRness are now being implemented. ECCSEL has started using the FUJI tool to test the measurement of FAIRness and evaluate its potential as a KPI instrument. In parallel, several individual KPIs based on the 17 core FAIR object assessment metrics are under review. Once ECCSEL expands its FAIR data offerings, these KPIs will be formally adopted and integrated into its monitoring framework.

6. Metadata management in stories project

The project addresses the fragmentation of research data caused by the infrastructures by adopting FAIR principles and ontology-driven metadata management. These measures ensure reproducibility, machine-readability, and interoperability across heterogeneous electrochemical energy storage datasets. High-throughput imaging and experimental techniques generate vast amounts of heterogeneous data that require FAIR-compliant metadata to become searchable, combinable, and usable for predictive AI models. Ontologies such as the European Materials Modelling Ontology (EMMO) and CHADA tables provide standardized vocabularies, resolving ambiguities in terminology (e.g., “Pt/C” vs. “Platinum on Carbon”) and enabling hierarchical queries across synthesis, characterization, and simulation workflows. Existing platforms like EOSC, FAIRsharing, and EERAdata provide registries and guidelines but do not yet offer seamless ingestion and ontology-aligned graph storage for imaging-based workflows but they can be employed as a guide for future developments.

Ensuring metadata quality and completeness is central to this approach. The project implements completeness scores to measure coverage of required fields, controlled-vocabulary compliance to validate entries against ontology terms, and provenance tracking to capture who, when, and why changes were made. Automated ingestion pipelines integrate these quality checks, supported by large language models that assist in mapping unmapped entries. This reduces manual error, guarantees interoperability, and prepares datasets for AI/ML training.

Community adoption and sustainability are addressed through stakeholder working groups that define metadata requirements, incentives from funders and journals to enforce FAIR compliance, and long-term curation teams that maintain ontologies and incorporate emerging modalities such as 4D tomography or operando spectroscopy. The ontology framework is modular, ensuring adaptability to new materials classes and workflows.

Building on CHADA, the project defines a modular metadata schema organized into six categories: organizational data, synthesis/fabrication, sample preparation, characterization parameters, preprocessing, and data analysis. Python classes automate ingestion of this schema into Neo4j, a graph-native database chosen for its ability to represent complex domains. Unlike rigid relational databases, Neo4j represents workflows as node sequences with properties and directed relationships, allowing flexible modelling of heterogeneous fabrication and characterization processes without altering the existing structure.

The framework is demonstrated through a pilot application that supports template-based metadata entry in CSV and JSON formats, hybrid querying via lexical and semantic search, and automated ingestion into the graph database. This is operationalized through the ViMi Labs platform, which provides collaborative lab spaces, role-based access, project tracking, and integration of Python-based modules. ViMi supports automated metadata collection, image annotation, and AI-driven

analysis pipelines for segmentation, detection, and super-resolution microscopy, thereby creating a closed loop between data capture and model training.

At the infrastructure level, the system integrates graph-based metadata management with AI-ready pipelines. Data ingested into ViMi is enriched through ontology alignment, stored in a FAIR-compliant repository, and made accessible through semantic and lexical search. Models can be containerized with standardized metadata to enable analytics, inverse design, or integration into device optimization workflows. ViMi also provides enterprise-grade FAIR data services, including automated ingestion of diverse file formats using LLM-based extraction and customizable knowledge graph visualization to benchmark materials, assess stability, and predict lifetimes.

Together, these components create an end-to-end FAIR pipeline that captures metadata, aligns it with ontologies, stores it in graph form, supports semantic search, and connects to AI model deployment. This holistic approach provides the technical foundation required to accelerate discovery, characterization, and optimization of materials in the energy storage domain.

Figure 1: Screenshots from StoRIES cloud platform: (left) example of metadata schema, (right) model execution deployment.

7. Business model

7.1 BUSINESS MODELS FOR RESEARCH DATA

The energy sector is undergoing a profound transformation driven by digitalization, creating new opportunities for innovation and business value creation. Emerging technologies such as digital twins, smart automation, and AI-based analytics enable more informed decision-making, higher operational efficiency, and optimized lifecycle management. This digital transition extends directly to energy storage and battery systems, where data-driven and AI-enhanced solutions are already improving materials design, manufacturing processes, and quality assurance.

At the core of this transformation lies data interoperability, which is essential to enable seamless integration and utilization of data across different platforms, technologies, and stakeholders. However, while data has often been described as the "new oil," this analogy is conceptually flawed. Unlike physical commodities, data is intangible, non-rivalrous, and easily replicable—its value depends on context, quality, and accessibility rather than scarcity. Furthermore, data protection, privacy management, and cybersecurity impose additional costs, while the absence of standardized valuation frameworks makes it difficult to determine the economic worth of energy-related data assets.

Consequently, robust business models for open and FAIR energy data are still emerging. There is a growing need to explore new paradigms such as data-as-a-service (DaaS), trusted data marketplaces, and collaborative data ecosystems that balance openness with value capture. For the energy storage research community, developing such models will be key to transforming high-quality data into sustainable economic and societal value, while supporting transparency, innovation, and European leadership in the digital energy transition.

7.2 IDENTIFYING AND DESIGNING BUSINESS MODELS

The task involves developing methods to assess the market value of data in the energy storage and battery systems industry. It explores business opportunities for a research institution, such as creating FAIR energy data and offering FAIRification services. Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) developed a business model Canvas (BMC), which is widely applied by practitioners and scientists alike. It can be used to design potential business models for established and niche markets alike. The latter is the case for data markets, as they are still in the initial stages of formation. The simple

structure of the BMC covers pivotal components of any business endeavour, including: 1) key partners, 2) key activities, 3) key resources, 4) value proposition, 5) customer relationships, 6) communication channels, 7) customer segments, 8) cost structure, and 9) revenue streams.

Figure 2: Business Model Canvas for the energy storage and battery systems industry. Source: Based on the general canvas of Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010).

The application of Osterwalder and Pigneur’s BMC to the case of data relevant to the energy storage and battery systems industry is shown in the Figure 2. It begins with the identification of key partners, which range from industrial users, research institutions, individual researchers, science funders, planners, and decision-makers to stakeholders external to the technological domain (e.g., data scientists, librarians, or the public). For a more in-depth analysis of the stakeholder landscape of energy systems, see Wierling et al, 2019. Key activities for research institutions engaged in the energy storage domain include the fabrication of data for new battery designs, as well as data curation and interpretation services (including FAIR data management). Similarly, key resources originate from superior domain knowledge, new research results, and expertise in solving FAIR data problems (e.g., in the creation of ontologies within and beyond the domain, the design of data curation workflows and FAIR data software). Offering these skills and resources leads to the value proposition for the domain, which lies in the economic benefits accrued from high-quality data, enabling the above-mentioned prospects, which are related to the deployment of smart technologies, elevated system efficiency, lowered costs for operation and maintenance or avoided costs to compensate for

environmental impacts. The discussion of how to obtain precise enough and consistent figures for revenues and costs connected to the commodity "data" follows below. What remains to be analysed regarding the general BMC structure are customer-related questions. All stakeholders can be seen as potential customers, but the industrial sector is deemed most interesting. An open question concerns communication channel: currently, there are no established channels for offering and transferring data to customers. While some platform concepts for the trade of energy data are being tried out (e.g., Open Subsurface Data Universe, see also later in this section), their maturity and sustainability have yet to be shown. The establishment of data market platforms is a crucial step for opening communication channels with potential customers.

7.3 VALUE OF DATA

Revenues in the data economy increasingly depend on the intrinsic and contextual value of data assets. Key determinants of this value include accessibility, interoperability, and accuracy, which are particularly critical for data generated in the battery and energy storage domains. These factors enable users to evaluate data provenance, assess reliability, and identify potential sources of error. However, the impact of these value drivers can vary significantly depending on the specific use case, and excessive or poorly curated data may lead to diminishing returns, undermining efficiency and analytical quality.

Data openness plays a pivotal role in shaping the potential economic and societal impact of energy storage research. Open and interoperable data foster cross-sector collaboration, innovation in materials and system design, and accelerated technology deployment by enabling diverse stakeholders—academia, industry, and policymakers—to build upon shared, high-quality datasets. At the same time, the creation of open data ecosystems supports new revenue models by improving existing business processes, enabling entry into adjacent markets, and facilitating the emergence of data-driven enterprises within the energy storage value chain.

While the adoption of interoperable and well-documented data practices enhances accuracy, consistency, and transparency, the quantification of data value remains complex. This challenge arises from uncertainties in the evolving energy storage market and the absence of standardized valuation frameworks. Approaches to data monetization may include:

- estimating the business value of data through expected operational or strategic benefits,
- calculating cost savings derived from improved efficiency and predictive analytics,
- conducting market analyses based on energy and materials pricing trends,
- performing benchmarking against transactions of comparable datasets, and
- assessing the replacement cost associated with reproducing equivalent data.

Overall, greater data openness within the energy storage community enhances not only scientific reproducibility and innovation potential, but also lays the foundation for sustainable, data-centric business models that can drive long-term value creation across the European energy ecosystem.

Table 1: Common data value drivers and the reasoning of their importance for the energy storage and battery systems industry

Data value driver	Data is more valuable ...
1) Exclusivity	... the more unique the data is. (e.g., owning a specific material database with insights into battery technologies)
2) Timeliness	... the timelier and up to date the data is. (e.g., having access to real-time data for the management of smart grids with storage solutions)
3) Accuracy	... the closer to reality the data is. (e.g., technically validated data)
4) Completeness	... the more thorough and finished the data is. (e.g., comprising a representative, detailed sample of battery solutions)
5) Consistency	... the FAIRER data standards are applied (e.g., data are tested against ISO standards, which are consistently applied)
6) General purpose	... the more flexible the use of the data is. (e.g., linking of data across domains with unique identifiers, combining governmental with private data)
7) Interoperability	... the easier the use and transfer of the data is. (e.g., acquiring FAIR data metrics, including user-centred documentation)
8) Accessibility	... the better they are found and accessed, by autonomously acting machines and protocols.
9) Liabilities and risk	... the less the liability and risks associated with the use of data are. (e.g., licensing for batteries and storage, risk management of their use)

8. Recommendations and outlook

The StoRIES project has successfully achieved all key objectives to define a **metadata framework** for the energy storage community. Moreover, a unified, FAIR-compliant protocol for energy storage data has been established, providing a standardized foundation for data management across diverse research domains all connected with energy storage. Furthermore, an **LLM-enhanced ontology alignment system**, implemented through graph database technologies, has been fully developed to enable advanced semantic search and interoperability. The approach has been validated through practical use cases, including life cycle assessment (LCA) and technology development analyses, demonstrating its robustness and applicability to real-world research challenges.

These accomplishments have already delivered significant impacts: accelerated research cycles, improved reproducibility, and enhanced AI-readiness through the provision of standardized, machine-actionable datasets. In alignment with its long-term vision, **StoRIES has successfully established a fully integrated, community-driven data ecosystem** that strengthens European competitiveness in the energy storage sector. This ecosystem enables seamless data interoperability, supports sustainable data governance through initiatives such as EOSC and EERA, and effectively balances open science principles with intellectual property protection. As a result, Europe is now better positioned as a global leader in energy storage innovation, underpinned by robust and scalable data infrastructures that foster collaboration and drive future discoveries.

The project has also fully implemented, in the frame of VIMLABs, a **AI-driven platform** to generate and update both a metadata and an ontology framework from both experimental and computational datasets in the energy storage field. Building upon existing ontologies and standards, the platform has created new metadata structures and vocabularies. By providing templates, controlled vocabularies, and detailed guidance for metadata entry, the StoRIES platform enables researchers to describe their data in a manner fully compliant with FAIR principles, ensuring high levels of interoperability and reusability.

Through the widespread adoption of standardized metadata, StoRIES has significantly improved data sharing, integration, and linkage among stakeholders within the European energy storage community, thereby laying the foundation for a more efficient, transparent, and collaborative research landscape.

However, implementing FAIR principles involves following a set of practical recommendations [ESFRI–EOSC Task Force, 2024] that can be adopted and properly implemented by the energy storage community. These recommendations are selected and adapted to promote consistent, transparent, and interoperable management of data across the heterogeneous energy storage sector.

- The energy storage community should adopt FAIR principles at **multiple scales**, ranging from materials to devices and full systems. Each specific case or level of analysis needs to be carefully considered when applying FAIR principles to ensure that the most suitable practices are used in each context.
- The community should ensure the availability of FAIR and open datasets to enhance data exchange through **common standards**. Establishing shared and standardized approaches to data management will facilitate collaboration and interoperability among different research teams, infrastructures, and stakeholders.
- In the energy storage domain, a key objective is to produce **high-quality FAIR data** that are also accessible to the public. Ensuring that datasets are well-documented, traceable, and open supports transparency, reproducibility, and broader scientific engagement.
- The energy storage community should promote the use and **sharing of reliable FAIR datasets** instead of relying on closed datasets. FAIR datasets improve trust, enable verification, and contribute to cumulative knowledge building, while closed data limit opportunities for innovation and collaboration.
- In line with European Union policy, both the **energy storage community and Member States** should guarantee data interoperability and access, particularly for FAIR data. Currently, access to certain datasets, such as those derived from battery management systems, remains restricted due to encryption practices and proprietary formats. These limitations should be addressed to foster more open and FAIR-aligned data sharing environments.
- The energy storage community should remove existing barriers and develop a comprehensive **policy strategy** for FAIR data sharing. Such a strategy should be based on systematic assessments of system flexibility, adequacy, and stability, as well as analyses of gaps within national regulatory frameworks. Proper identification of flexibility requirements by country and by time frame is crucial for evaluating how FAIR data can contribute to future energy storage technologies. A key objective should be the convergence of data quality and coverage among storage facilities, public databases, and existing power plant datasets, thereby improving transparency and accessibility of energy-related information.
- Within the energy storage sector, developing policy implementation mechanisms and transforming the **research culture** remain major challenges for achieving FAIR certification. **Strengthening partnerships** between research institutions, industry, and policymakers is essential to expand FAIR data accessibility and to ensure compliance with data management requirements. The successful implementation of FAIR principles depends on sustained collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, technology providers, research departments, and funding bodies [Mietchen, 2022; Nitecki & Alter, 2021].
- Through the process of FAIRification, data assets are transformed into **structured data products that can be exchanged or even traded** within emerging data markets. FAIRification enhances data reusability and optimizes data consumption across different sectors and user groups. Importantly, the level of FAIRification should be adapted to the needs of specific customer segments, ensuring relevance and usability for each intended audience.
- The **value of a data** asset fundamentally depends on its quality. Applying FAIR principles provides a consistent framework for assessing data quality, thereby establishing a metric for reliability and

value. This, in turn, supports the potential monetization of data and encourages the development of sustainable data ecosystems.

- **Governmental institutions and funding organizations** are encouraged to support the creation and maintenance of data markets and platforms, as well as to promote their use. This support could include funding projects that aim to develop and test methods for quantifying the costs and benefits of research data, contributing to the establishment of transparent and economically viable data-sharing ecosystems.
- Current funding policies often restrict the exploration of new or untested areas of research, as they prioritize minimizing and mitigating project risks. This cautious approach can delay the generation of research insights and slow down the translation of innovative FAIR and open data solutions into practical applications. Opening funding approaches toward **more flexible and adaptive risk management frameworks** would help accelerate innovation and reduce the time needed to bring FAIR and open data services to the market.

Following these recommendations will significantly contribute to advancing openness and FAIRness across the energy storage community. Standardizing data formats, improving interoperability, and integrating domain-specific training tailored to the needs and practices of researchers and stakeholders in this field will help overcome current barriers and ensure effective implementation of FAIR data principles.

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Appendix I

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for **Research Infrastructures (RIs)**

1. **Scientific & Research Impact**

- **Publications:** Number and quality of peer-reviewed scientific papers produced by users of the RI.
- **Citations:** Frequency of citation of research using the RI, which reflects its contribution to advancing knowledge.
- **Innovative Outputs:** Patents, prototypes, or new methodologies that emerge from the RI's research activities.
- **Interdisciplinary Research:** The extent to which the RI facilitates cross-disciplinary work and new research areas.

2. **User Engagement & Access**

- **User Numbers:** The number of researchers, institutions, or industries using the RI (can be broken down by country, sector, etc.).
- **Access Frequency:** How often researchers access the RI's facilities or resources (e.g., hours of use, number of experiments conducted).
- **Diversity of Users:** Percentage of users from various sectors (e.g., academic, industrial, public, SMEs) or geographical regions.
- **User Satisfaction:** Surveys or feedback indicating how satisfied users are with the RI, including the quality of the facilities, support, and results.

3. **Operational Efficiency & Availability**

- **Up-time / Downtime:** The availability of the RI's facilities, equipment, or platforms. High uptime indicates well-maintained systems and reliability.
- **Facility Utilization:** Measures how much the infrastructure's capacity is being utilized (e.g., number of available hours vs. hours in use).
- **Turnaround Time:** Time taken from a user's request to access the infrastructure to the actual provision of resources or data.
- **Operational Costs:** The efficiency of operating the RI, including cost per user or cost per research project.

4. **Innovation & Technological Advancement**

- **New Technologies Developed:** Number of novel technologies or solutions developed with the help of the RI.
- **Technology Transfer:** The commercialization or transfer of RI-based innovations to industry (e.g., new products, spin-off companies).
- **Collaborations with Industry:** The number of collaborations or partnerships with private-sector entities, especially for technology development or commercialization.

5. **Sustainability & Environmental Impact**

- **Energy Efficiency:** How much energy the infrastructure consumes relative to its outputs (e.g., research data, user access hours).
- **Carbon Footprint:** Emissions resulting from the operation of the infrastructure, including energy use, transportation, etc.
- **Circularity:** Adoption of sustainable practices, like waste recycling or reuse of resources.

6. Impact on Education & Training

- **Training Hours:** Number of hours dedicated to training users on how to use the RI's resources effectively.
- **Capacity Building:** Number of young researchers or new PhDs trained via the RI, including workshops, seminars, and hands-on training.
- **Workshops & Courses:** Number of educational and outreach events hosted or sponsored by the RI.

7. Societal & Economic Impact

- **Societal Impact:** Contributions to addressing societal challenges (e.g., health, climate, energy sustainability). This could be qualitative (policy influence, societal awareness) or quantitative (direct solutions, services).
- **Economic Impact:** Job creation, GDP contribution, new businesses, or innovation clusters resulting from the RI.
- **Public Outreach:** The number of public talks, media mentions, or events that engage with non-specialist audiences.

8. Financial Sustainability

- **Revenue Generation:** Total income or revenue generated by the RI through user fees, grants, collaborations, or commercialization.
- **Funding Diversification:** Diversity of funding sources (e.g., EU, national, industry, philanthropic), ensuring long-term sustainability.
- **Cost Efficiency:** Comparison of the operational costs to the research outputs and innovations created, indicating a good return on investment (ROI).

9. Global Collaboration & Recognition

- **International Partnerships:** Number of collaborative projects with international organizations, institutes, or governments.
- **Recognition in Global Rankings:** Position in international rankings or frameworks (e.g., QS, Times Higher Education for research excellence).
- **Contribution to Global Challenges:** Engagement with global initiatives, like the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

10. Governance & Strategic Alignment

- **Compliance with Regulations:** Adherence to legal and regulatory frameworks (e.g., EU regulations, ethical standards).
- **Alignment with Strategic Objectives:** The degree to which the infrastructure meets the goals outlined in national or regional research agendas.

- **Management and Transparency:** Quality of governance, including management efficiency, accountability, and transparency of operations and funding.

FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics

Source: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>, FAIRsFAIR “Fostering FAIR Data Practices In Europe” project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 under the Grant agreement 831558.

Listed below are the **seventeen minimum viable metrics** proposed by FAIRsFAIR for the systematic assessment of FAIR data objects¹ and detailed in the report **FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics** (v0.4). These metrics are based on indicators proposed by the **RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group**, on the **WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use checklist**, and on prior work conducted by project partners such as **FAIRdata** and **FAIREnough**.

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.

A data object may be assigned a globally unique identifier such that it can be referenced unambiguously by humans or machines. Globally unique means an identifier should be associated with only one resource at any time. Examples of unique identifiers of data are Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI), Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) such as URL and URN, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the Handle System, identifiers.org, w3id.org, and Archival Resource Key (ARK). A data repository may assign a globally unique identifier to your data or metadata when you publish and make it available through its curation service.

FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.

In this specification, we distinguish between the uniqueness and persistence of an identifier. An HTTP URL (the address of a given unique resource on the web) is globally unique but may not be persistent as the URL of data may not be accessible (link rot problem) or the data available under the original URL may be changed (content drift problem). Identifiers based on, e.g., the Handle System, DOI, ARK are both globally unique and persistent. They are maintained and governed such that they remain stable and resolvable for the long term. The persistent identifier (PID) of a data object may be resolved (point) to a landing page with metadata containing further information on how to access the data content, in some cases, a downloadable artefact, or none if the data or repository is no longer maintained. Therefore, ensuring persistence is a shared responsibility between a PID service provider (e.g., data cite) and its clients (e.g., data repositories). For example, the DOI system guarantees the persistence of its identifiers through its social (e.g., policy) and technical infrastructures, whereas a data provider ensures the availability of the resource (e.g., landing page, downloadable artefact) associated with the identifier.

FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary, and keywords) to support data findability.

Metadata is descriptive information about a data object. Since the metadata required differs depending on the users and their applications, this metric focuses on core metadata. The core metadata is the minimum descriptive information required to enable data finding, including citation, which makes it easier to find data. We determine the required metadata based on common data citation guidelines (e.g., DataCite, ESIP, and IASSIST), and metadata recommendations for data discovery (e.g., EOSC Datasets Minimum Information (EDMI), DataCite Metadata Schema, W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices, and Data Catalog Vocabulary).

This metric focuses on domain-agnostic core metadata. Domain or discipline-specific metadata specifications are covered under metric FsF-R1.3-01M. A repository should adopt a schema that includes properties of core metadata, whereas data authors should take the responsibility of providing core metadata.

FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.

The metadata should explicitly specify the identifier of the data such that users can discover and access the data through the metadata. If the identifier specified is persistent and points to a landing page, the data identifier, and links to download the data content should be considered in the assessment.

FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.

This metric refers to ways through which the metadata of data is exposed or provided in a standard and machine-readable format. Assessing this metric will require an understanding of the capabilities offered by the data repository used to host the data. Metadata may be available through multiple endpoints. For example, if data is hosted by a repository, the repository may disseminate its metadata through a metadata harvesting protocol (e.g., via OAI-PMH) and/or a web service. Metadata may also be embedded as structured data on a data page for use by web search engines such as Google and Bing or be available as linked (open) data.

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.

This metric determines if the metadata includes the level of access to the data, such as public, embargoed, restricted, or metadata-only access, and its access conditions. Both access level and conditions are necessary information to potentially gain access to the data. It is recommended that data should be as open as possible and as closed, as necessary.

- There are no access conditions for public data. Datasets should be released into the public domain (e.g., with an appropriate public-domain-equivalent license such as Creative Commons CC0 license) and openly accessible without restrictions, when possible.
- Embargoed access refers to data that will be made publicly accessible at a specific date. For example, a data author may release their data after having published their findings from the data. Therefore, access conditions such as the date the data will be released publicly is essential and should be specified in the metadata.

- Restricted access refers to data that can be accessed under certain conditions (e.g., because of commercial, sensitive, or other confidentiality reasons or the data is only accessible via a subscription or a fee). Restricted data may be available to a particular group of users or after permission is granted. For restricted data, the metadata should include the conditions of access to the data such as point of contact or instructions to access the data.
- Metadata-only access refers to data that is not made publicly available and for which only metadata is publicly available.

FsF-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.

Given an identifier of a dataset, the metadata of the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol. Consider, for example, the application layer protocols such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, TFTP, SFTP and AtomPub. Avoid disseminating metadata using a proprietary protocol (e.g., Apple Filing Protocol).

FsF-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.

Given an identifier of a dataset, the dataset should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, TFTP, SFTP, FTAM and AtomPub. Avoid disseminating data using a proprietary protocol.

FsF-A2-01M - Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.

This metric determines whether the metadata will be preserved even when the data, they represent are no longer available, replaced, or lost. Like metric FsF-F4-01M, answering this metric will require an understanding of the capabilities offered, data preservation plan, and policies implemented by the data repository and data services (e.g., Datacite PID service). Continued access to metadata depends on a data repository’s preservation practice, which is usually documented in the repository’s service policies or statements. A trustworthy data repository offering DOIs and implementing a PID Policy should guarantee that metadata will remain accessible even when data is no longer available for any reason (e.g., by providing a tombstone page).

FsF-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.

Knowledge representation is vital for machine-processing of the knowledge of a domain. Expressing the metadata of a data object using a formal knowledge representation will enable machines to process it in a meaningful way and enable more data exchange possibilities. Examples of knowledge representation languages are RDF, RDFS, and OWL. These languages may be serialized (written) in different formats. For instance, RDF/XML, RDFa, Notation3, Turtle, N-Triples and N-Quads, and JSON-LD are RDF serialization formats.

FsF-I1-02M - Metadata uses semantic resources.

A metadata document or selected parts of the document may incorporate additional terms from semantic resources (also referred to as semantic artefacts) that unambiguously describe the contents

so they can be processed automatically by machines. This metadata enrichment may facilitate enhanced data search and interoperability of data from diverse sources. Ontology, thesaurus, and taxonomy are kinds of semantic resources, and they come with varying degrees of expressiveness and computational complexity. Knowledge organization schemes such as thesaurus and taxonomy are semantically less formal than ontologies.

FsF-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.

Linking data to its related entities will increase its potential for reuse. The linking information should be captured as part of the metadata. A dataset may be linked to its prior version, related datasets, or resources (e.g., publication, physical sample, funder, repository, platform, site, or observing network registries). Links between data and its related entities should be expressed through relation types (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema specifies relation types between research objects through the fields ‘RelatedIdentifier’ and ‘RelationType’) and preferably use persistent Identifiers for related entities (e.g., ORCID for contributors, DOI for publications, and ROR for institutions).

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

This metric evaluates if the content of the dataset is specified in the metadata, and it should be an accurate reflection of the actual data deposited. Examples of the properties specifying data content are resource type (e.g., data or a collection of data), variable(s) measured or observed, method, data format, and size. Ideally, ontological vocabularies should be used to describe data content (e.g., variable) to support interdisciplinary reuse.

FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.

This metric evaluates if data is associated with a license because, otherwise, users cannot reuse it in a clear legal context. We encourage the application of licenses for all kinds of data, whether public, restricted or for specific users. Without an explicit license, users do not have a clear idea of what can be done with your data. Licenses can be of standard type (Creative Commons, Open Data Commons Open Database License) or bespoke licenses, and rights statements which indicate the conditions under which data can be reused.

It is highly recommended to use a standard, machine-readable license that can be interpreted by machines and humans. To inform users about what rights they must use a dataset; the license information should be specified as part of the dataset’s metadata.

FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.

Data provenance (also known as lineage) represents a dataset’s history, including the people, entities, and processes involved in its creation, management, and longer-term curation. Data producers must provide provenance information about the data to enable informed use and reuse. The levels of provenance information needed can vary depending on the data type (e.g., measurement, observation, derived data, or data product) and research domains. For that reason, it is difficult to define a set of finite provenance properties that will be adequate for all domains. Based

on existing work, we suggest that the following provenance properties of data generation or collection be included in the metadata record as a minimum.

- Sources of data, e.g., datasets, the data is derived from, and instruments.
- Data creation or collection date
- Contributors involved in data creation and their roles.
- Data publication, modification, and versioning information

There are numerous ways through which provenance information may be included in a metadata record. Some of the provenance properties (e.g., instrument, contributor) may be best represented using PIDs (such as DOIs for data, ORCIDs for researchers). This way, humans and systems can retrieve more information about each of the properties by resolving the PIDs. Alternatively, the provenance information can be given in a linked provenance record expressed explicitly in, e.g., PROV-O or PAV or Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VOID).

FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.

In addition to core metadata required to support data discovery (covered under metric FsF-F2-01M), metadata to support data reusability should be made available following community-endorsed metadata standards. Some communities have well-established metadata standards (e.g., geospatial: ISO19115; biodiversity: DarwinCore, ABCD, EML; social science: DDI; astronomy: International Virtual Observatory Alliance Technical Specifications) while others have limited standards or standards that are under development (e.g., engineering and linguistics). The use of community-endorsed metadata standards is usually encouraged and supported by domain and discipline-specific repositories.

FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.

File formats refer to methods for encoding digital information. For example, CSV for tabular data, NetCDF for multidimensional data, and GeoTIFF for raster imagery. Data should be made available in a file format that is backed by the research community to enable data sharing and reuse. Consider, for example, file formats that are widely used and supported by commonly used software and tools. These formats should also be suitable for long-term storage and archiving, which is usually recommended by a data repository. The formats not only give a higher certainty that your data can be read in the future, but they will also help to increase the reusability and interoperability. Using community-endorsed formats enables data to be loaded directly into the software and tools used for data analysis. It makes it possible to easily integrate your data with other data using the same preferred format. The use of community-endorsed formats will also help to transform the format to a newer one, in case an older format gets outdated.

Table 2: Fuji KPIs per category

Category	Key Performance Indicator	Focus Area
Scientific Impact	Publications, Citations	Research quality and dissemination

User Engagement	User Numbers, Access Frequency	Access to resources and user satisfaction
Operational Efficiency	Facility Utilization, Downtime	System reliability and resource optimization
Innovation & Technology	Tech Development, Transfer	Innovation rate and commercial applications
Sustainability	Energy Efficiency, Carbon Footprint	Environmental impact of RI operations
Education & Training	Training Hours, Workshops	Capacity building and educational outreach
Societal & Economic Impact	Economic Impact, Public Outreach	Broader societal value and economic contribution
Financial Sustainability	Revenue Generation, Cost Efficiency	Economic viability and funding stability
Global Recognition	International Partnerships, Rankings	Global presence and influence
Governance	Compliance, Transparency	Operational effectiveness and accountability

Table 3: ECCSEL KPI’s

Topic	Description	KPI	Target value	Priority	Source of info	Owner	Status	Steps needed / performed
Creation of new concepts	Needs for research infrastructure: existing RI upgrades & new	KP1 - Number of reports on agreed upgrade and new facilities		5				
	Inputs from industry	KP2 – Number of workshops with industrial parties		5				
	Technology, scientific excellence, documentation from the ECCSEL Operations Centre	KP3 - Technology scientific excellence documentation/report on gaps		5				
Managing knowledge resources and research infrastructure	Performance and benefit analyses of ECCSEL RI	KP4 - Satisfied customers		5				
	Use of facilities and resources	KP5 - Number of ECCSEL research facilities used, transnational and national access		5				
	Membership development/expansion	KP6 - Number of partner countries		5				

Table 4: External visible KPIs

Topic	Description	KPI	Target value	Priority	Source of info	Owner	Status	Steps needed
Creation of new concepts	Strategy planning of ECCSEL IR	KPI- A - Number of internal strategy theme meetings		3				
		KPI - B - Technology coordination in RICC meetings		4				
Deployment and demonstration	Strengthen business partner involvement	KPI - C - Collaboration agreements providing access to industrial pilot plants		2 (initially)				
		KPI - D - Number of industrial users/funders involved, including from power generation		3				
	Capacity building	KPI- E - Number of capacity building events		4				

Table 5:ESFRI Landmark KPI’s

Objective	ESFRI KPI
Enabling scientific excellence+A4	1. Total number of users granted access per year
	2. Total number of projects per year
	3. Total number of publications related to facilities (and to access) per year
	4. Number of high TRL projects (TRL 7-9) each year
	5. Total number of upgrades and new facilities built per year
	6. Total number of additional (existing) facilities per year
	7. Total number of facilities listed on the Infrastructure Development Plan (IDP) added per year
	8. Average customer satisfaction rating per year
	9. Total number of projects led by master's (and bachelor's) / PhD students or where they participate per year
Delivery of education and training	10. Total number of persons receiving training as part of the facility access
	11. For ECCSEL Operations Centre and ECCSELERATE level only: Number of persons attending online training and accessing recorded training sessions each year
	12. Total number of members, associated members, observers
Enhancing collaboration in Europe	13. Number of participating countries per year; Number of not ESFRI-associated members per year
	14. Total number of (lead) users per ESFRI country per year
	15. Total number of projects with industrial partners or led by an industrial company per year
Outreach to the public	16. Number of events (and possibly participants) and facility tours with participants from schools, general public visitors, and politicians per year
	17. Outreach through media
	18. Total number of recipients of newsletter and / visitors to homepage/clicks on ECCSEL YouTube per year; Number of LinkedIn followers
	19. Number of publicly available data sets used externally
Optimising data use	20. Total number of data users per year
Provision of scientific advice	21. Number of events ECCSEL is presenting where policy makers are present each year
	22. ECCSEL is named in National Roadmaps in ECCSEL member countries and in 4-5 countries targeted for future membership
	23. Now for access to facilities: Total number of granted proposals/accepted users from non-ESFRI countries per year
Facilitating international cooperation	24. Number of international (non-ESFRI) persons receiving training (TA visits, webinar attendance) per year
	25. Number of actual facility usage days per year
Optimising management	26. Investments of current and new facility owners in facility upgrades and in new build facilities per year
	27. Average customer satisfaction rating per year
Enabling scientific excellence	

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